

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

Badan Sabina.

Degree: medical student

Mazur-Nicorici Lucia

Degree: University professor of the department of cardiology;

Place of Work: State University of Medicine and Pharmacy „Nicolae Testemițanu”

Abstract

Hypertension is high blood pressure, equal to or greater than 140/90 mmHg at rest in adults taken in medical office conditions. Adequate control of hypertension is essential to prevent cardiovascular events. The frequency of arterial hypertension increases with age, with a prevalence > 60% in people aged > 60 years.

We aimed to estimate the studies analyzing the socio-economic status and types of measurement in patients with arterial hypertension. For this, we used articles and scientific publications from the databases PubMed, Medscape, published during the years 2016-2021, using both the Romanian and English languages in the electronic databases.

We also aimed to assess the socio-economic status of patients with arterial hypertension by prioritizing the main components: education, income and occupation. Likewise, comparison of the socio-economic status of patients with arterial hypertension from both urban and rural areas;

The overall results provided evidence of an increased risk of hypertension among the lowest socioeconomic categories. It has been shown that men tend to develop hypertension around the age of 45, while women later.

Our results indicated an increased prevalence of hypertension among the lowest SES. Education, an important indicator of socio-economic status, would have the strongest association with the prevalence of hypertension.

Keyword: Arterial hypertension, socio-economic status, risk factors.

Introduction

Arterial hypertension is one of the most widespread diseases of the cardiovascular system. During the last decades, it remains a major problem both in the general structure of diseases at the global level and as an important risk factor in various chronic pathologies such as kidney diseases, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and cancer, demonstrated by its high level of mortality and morbidity.

According to the guidelines of the European Society of Cardiology, published in 2018, blood pressure can be measured in the doctor's office, at home or by ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (AMB). In all cases, it is important that blood pressure measurement is done with a validated instrument [2].

The prevalence of HTN in adults is approximately 30-45%, with a standardized global prevalence across all ages of 24% for men and 20% for women in 2015 [1].

The prevalence and complications associated with HTN are multifactorial, such as family history, presence of obesity, misdiagnosis, and irrelevant or insufficient therapy. We also distinguish the factors of first importance: hypercholesterolemia, smoking, hyperglycemia, alcohol consumption, sedentary lifestyle and obesity. The incidence of cardiovascular disease in the population is proportional to lifestyle and modifiable cardiovascular risk factors, as well as their association.

Sodium is an essential nutrient and dietary requirement for all humans [3]. When an excess of salt is administered, there is an increase in volume as well as the modulation of cellular baroreceptors to the action of vasopressor substances. With the administration of less

than 3g of sodium daily, other mechanisms are involved in the pathogenesis of HTN, the activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system plays a critical role in this respect [3]. A cohort study that included 12,550 people, prospectively, suggested that the occurrence of type II diabetes was almost 2.5 times more frequent in people with HTN than in normotensive ones [4]. Both hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia activate the renin-angiotensin system, by increasing the expression of angiotensinogen, angiotensin II and the AT1 receptor, which together can contribute to the development of hypertension in patients with insulin resistance [5]. Increased cholesterol is one of the factors that predispose people to cardiovascular diseases, being responsible for 2.6 million deaths annually. The presence of high blood pressure and high cholesterol in the blood is a dangerous combination that can result in severe complications such as atherosclerosis and cardiovascular diseases. Studies demonstrate a direct association of body mass index (BMI) with BP [6]. The risk of hypertension increases continuously with increasing anthropometric measurements (waist circumference, waist-to-hip ratio and waist-to-height ratio) in parallel with BMI. A threefold or greater increase in obesity has been observed in lower socioeconomic status groups due to urbanization, changes in food supply and diet, and reduced physical activity [7]. Smoking has been described as a major global risk factor for various cardiovascular diseases, including stroke, peripheral vascular disease, coronary heart disease, hypertension, and cancer. Moderate to heavy drinkers have been consistently shown to have a higher risk of developing HTN [8].

Among the social determinants of hypertension, individual socioeconomic status, including education,

income, and occupation, may be crucial for hypertension management (prevalence, awareness, treatment, and control) [9]. Material circumstances (such as housing and access to food), behavioral factors (such as diet, exercise, smoking, and alcohol consumption), and psychological factors are examples of intermediate components of SES that contribute to the development of hypertension (eg, factors of stress, social isolation and loneliness). These determinants as well as other behavioral factors such as treatment compliance, which may be influenced by state-level factors such as the quality of national health systems, may also affect how well a person's hypertension is controlled. people. The association between education and the incidence of hypertension in high-income countries is relatively constant. For example, a meta-analysis reported that lower educational attainment is associated with an increased prevalence of hypertension in high-income countries [9] [10] [11]. A national survey using a sample of 4911 people residing in Portugal described the highest rates of HTN in men, in people aged 65 to 74 years, and in people with a low level of education and the unemployed [11]. Another 4-year study from Korea demonstrated that subjects with a higher level of education and higher income had a lower prevalence of hypertension [13].

In accordance with the proposed aim and objectives, we created a study group composed of 60 patients, average age 62.25 years, with the definitive diagnosis of arterial hypertension, established in accordance with the study inclusion criteria. The included patients are aged between 45 and 63 years old, hospitalized between 2021 and 2022. The research took place on the basis of questionnaires, developed in advance. Patients were evaluated on the basis of questionnaires, which were developed in advance, which included general and special methods of clinical examination, as well as data from the patient's clinical observation sheets. The general assessment included: the patient's personal data (surname, first name, age and year of birth, place of residence – urban/rural, apartment/house on land), family status and education. Patients also provided data on their official monthly income and whether they had any additional income (financial assistance from parents/children or any other source of additional money). Glucose assessment was performed fasting by collecting capillary blood, with reference indices <6.1 mmol/l, values exceeding ≥ 5.6 mmol/l or 102 mg/dl, represent one of the criteria for inclusion in the notion of syndrome metabolically, and levels ≥ 7 mmol/l, on repeated measurements, denote the presence of diabetes.

Several scales have been proposed to classify populations by socioeconomic status: Rahudkar scale 1960, Udai Parikh scale 1964, Jalota scale 1970, Kulshrestha scale 1972, Kuppuswamy scale 1976, Shrivastava scale 1978, Bharadwaj scale 2001. These scales being specific for certain geographical areas, they are not applicable for the Republic of Moldova.

In this context, according to the data obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova, we proposed to quantify the average monthly gross salary per capita in 2 categories. Obtaining data such as the average gross monthly salary is 10,648.1 lei,

we decided to divide the income declared by the patients in the study group into 2 categories, namely: • Less than 10,648 lei; • More than 10,648 lei.

Conclusions

Low socio-economic status is associated with marked hypertension, and this association is especially influenced by the level of education; thus, it is important to identify and monitor hypertension in order to reduce the risk of high blood pressure among the most vulnerable groups in different countries and societies. Poor socioeconomic circumstances during life are also noted, such as unfavorable environmental conditions at the workplace, including at the place of living, insecurity at work, which negatively affects people's health and life. From the researched risk factors, we mention the importance of obesity in the development of HTN, and following the research we obtained a negative result on the control of obesity and sedentarism. From the whole group of patients, only 8 (11.43%) patients have normal weight according to BMI. After analyzing the collected data, we obtained 28 smoking patients (40%) and 7 ex-smoking patients (10%). Also, 40 patients (57.14%) reported not consuming alcohol at all. From the researched sample, from the total number of patients with diabetes, we observe a trend in correcting the blood sugar level with the help of diet (11.43%).

Social determinants of hypertension, such as individual socioeconomic status, including education, income, and occupation, are central to the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of hypertension. The level of education is the key moment in affecting the quality of human life, with the aim of improving life expectancy. As a result of our research, we obtained the results: patients with completed secondary education predominate, 61%; patients with higher education are 37%; and no studies in general reported one patient. Another pillar of HTA is occupation. We received the results: 44 patients employed in the field of work, 14 unemployed patients, 12 patients with a degree of disability of which 7 are employed and 5 unemployed. According to the collected data, a higher percentage is found in people with a salary of less than 10,600 lei, i.e. 51 patients (72.85%) have reported monthly incomes lower than those presented by the National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova.

References

1. National Clinical Protocol – High Blood Pressure in Adults 2020
2. Bryan Williams, Giuseppe Mancia et al. 2018 ESC/ESH Guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension: The Task Force for the management of arterial hypertension of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the European Society of Hypertension (ESH).
3. O'Donnell M, Mente A, Yusuf S. Sodium intake and cardiovascular health. *Circ Res* 2015;116:1046–57
4. Nadar SK, Tayebjee MH, Messerli F, Lip GY. Target organ damage in hypertension: pathophysiology and implications for drug therapy. // *Curr Pharm Des*. 2006, Vol. 12, № 13, p.1581-1592

5. Malhotra A., Kang B. P. S., Cheung S., Opawumi D., Meggs L. G., Angiotensin II promotes glucose-induced activation of cardiac protein kinase C isozymes and phosphorylation of troponin I. // *Diabetes*, 2001, vol. 50, № 8, p. 1918–1926.
6. Jayedi A, Rashidy-Pour A, Khorshidi M, Shab-Bidar S. Body mass index, abdominal adiposity, weight gain and risk of developing hypertension: a systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis of more than 2.3 million participants. *Obes Rev* 2018;19:654–67.
7. Prevention and Control of Hypertension: JACC Health Promotion Series 2018
8. Alcohol and Hypertension—New Insights and Lingering Controversies Ian B. Puddey¹ & Trevor A. Mori¹ & Anne E. Barden¹ & Lawrence J. Beilin¹ pag 1-2
9. Nakagomi, A., Yasufuku, Y., Ueno, T. et al. Social determinants of hypertension in high-income countries: A narrative literature review and future directions. *Hypertens Res* 45, 1575–1581 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41440-022-00972-7>
10. Liew SJ, Lee JT, Tan CS, Koh CHG, Van Dam R, Müller-Riemenschneider F. Sociodemographic factors in relation to hypertension prevalence, awareness, treatment and control in a multi-ethnic Asian population: a cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*. 2019;9:e025869.
11. Rodrigues AP, Gaio V, Kislaya I, Graff-Iversen S, Cordeiro E, Silva AC, Namorado S, Barreto M, Gil AP, Antunes L, Santos A, Miguel JP, Nunes B, Dias CM; INSEF Research group. Sociodemographic disparities in hypertension prevalence: Results from the first Portuguese National Health Examination Survey. *Rev Port Cardiol (Engl Ed)*. 2019 Aug;38(8):547-555. English, Portuguese. doi: 10.1016/j.repc.2018.10.012. Epub 2019 Nov 8. PMID: 31708247.
12. Henke N., Schmidt-Ullrich R., Dechend. R., Park J., Qadri F., Wellner M., Obst M., Gross V., Dietz R., Luft F.C., Scheidereit C., Muller D.N., Vascular Endothelial Cell-Specific NF-κB Suppression Attenuates Hypertension-Induced Renal Damage. // *Circulation Research*, 2007, Vol. 101, p. 268-276.
13. Piskorz, D. Hypertensive Mediated Organ Damage and Hypertension Management. How to Assess Beneficial Effects of Antihypertensive Treatments?. *High Blood Press Cardiovasc Prev* 27, 9–17 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40292-020-00361-6>